

A Cross-Sectional Study for Assessment of Factors Related to Acute Respiratory Infection in Pre-School Children in an Urban SlumRavi Nandini Singh¹, Ram Kumar Himanshu²¹Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, IMS, BHU, Varanasi, U.P. -221005²Retd. Professor, Department of Pediatrics, VMMC, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Acute respiratory infection is a major public health problem particularly in developing countries like India where most of people belong to poor economic strata and reside in slums and are exposed to fatal illnesses. Under-five children are particularly vulnerable to this Sort of infections and it has posed a great economic burden to the developing world particularly in the urban slums. Aim of this study to assess prevalence of acute respiratory infections amongst children in an urban slum; sociodemographic profile of study population and assess health seeking behaviour of parents for these morbidities.

Methods: It was a Cross-sectional study carried out in 256 under-five children which was conducted in vulnerable urban slum in UHC field practice area of tertiary care hospital for 12 months duration.

Results: The overall prevalence of ARI was found to be 30.4%. Children in age group of 1-3 years were most commonly affected with ARI (57.1%). In social class IV & V, prevalence of ARI was highest with 40.70 %. There was a significant association between immunization status, birth weight, family composition, malnutrition status and Occurrence of ARI in under-five children.

Conclusion: The present study found poor birth weight, low socio economic class, delay in initiation of breast feeding, pre-lacteal feeding, and immunization status as significant risk factors for ARI in under-fives.

Keywords: Acute respiratory infection (ARI), Urban Slum, Cross sectional study, under five children.

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Introduction

Progress of nation is not only judged by its economic growth but also by how much weaker section of community receives care and support during most vulnerable period i.e. childhood wherein growth and development occurs in various dimensions and child needs special attention and care.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set the target to end deaths from preventable diseases among new-borns and children under five years old by 2030 (Dahan & Gelb, 2015).

Nevertheless, in 2017, an estimated 5.5 million children belonging to this age group died from preventable diseases (Hug et al., 2018). One of the impediments to achieve this goal adopted by all United Nations member states is the high prevalence of acute respiratory infection (ARI), a leading cause of childhood morbidity and mortality. In 2016, from 68.06 million episodes, an estimated 652 572 children aged below five years died because of lower respiratory infections (Troeger et al., 2018; Walker et al., 2013) reported that the incidence of severe ARI is the highest in Southeast Asian and African regions. India is one of the 15 highest burdened countries in terms of total pneu-

monia episodes and related childhood mortality. In India, around 400 000 children aged below five years die every year from ARI-related diseases. The figure accounts for 13–16% of all child deaths among paediatric hospital admissions (Jain et al., 2001; Vashishtha, 2010). As a cause of approximately one-fourth of global annual deaths of children aged below five years, ARI is a significant public health concern in India (Mathew et al., 2011). On this basis, one million deaths among under-fives in our Country are due to ARI and most of these occur in infants.[1] Cause specific mortality due to ARI is 10 to 50 times higher in developing countries than developed countries.[1] In our country, 14.3% of deaths during infancy and 15.9% of deaths between 1-5 years of age are due to ARI. [2] In India, pneumonias are estimated to be responsible for 75% of ARI deaths. [3]

Estimating the morbidity burden has inherent challenges due to lack of uniformity in study definitions, spectral nature of illness and misclassification errors. Recent estimates suggest 3.5% of the global burden of disease were caused by ARI. [3] In developing countries, on an average every child

had five episodes of ARI/year accounting for 30%-50% of the total paediatric outpatient visits and 20%-30% of the paediatric admissions. [2] India had been predicted to have over 700 million episodes of ARI and over 52 million episodes of pneumonia every year. [2] Studies in developing countries have identified risk factors to be among others over-crowding, nutritional factors, Parental Education, Socioeconomic status, poor housing condition, sex of child. Population in the urban slums is a heterogeneous conglomerate of all caste, creed, and religion with a diversified lifestyle. In addition, the risk factors for childhood ARI is also present in respect to the environmental, socioeconomic, and health seeking behaviour of the inhabitants. [4]

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted amongst the children below 5 years of age, living in urban slum area of an urban health centre attached to IMS, BHU, Varanasi, U.P. involving 256 children. Multistage simple random sampling was done and data was collected from informants using a semi structured pre-validated questionnaire after obtaining informed consent, by house visits over a period

of one year. The data hence collected was studied and study identified a high prevalence of ARI among under-fives and pointed out various socio-demographic, nutritional, and environmental factors as the modifiable risk factors and recommendation were made based on statistical analysis which would help to strengthen the approach towards paediatric care.

Data was analysed using MS excel and SPSS software version 17. Chi-square test was for finding association and p-value (<0.05) was considered significant.

History of nasal discharge, cough, cold, fever and sore throat, breathing difficulty, any discharge from ear alone or in combination was used in recognition of an episode of ARI. An absence of symptoms for three days or more was the criteria used for differentiating one episode from other.

Respiratory rate >60/minute (among children <2months), RR>50 (2-11 months), >40 (12-60 months), in case with cough, running nose or fever, singly or in combination was the criteria for recognition of the Severity of ARI.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristic wise sample distribution and prevalence of Acute Respiratory Infection in under-five children

Variable		Sample	ARI Case	χ^2 P-value
Age	12 months or less	51(19.9%)	10(13.00%)	$\chi^2= 0.121$ Df-2 p-value=0.941
	13-36 months	131(51.2%)	44(57.10%)	
	37-60 months	74(28.9%)	23(29.90%)	
Sex	Male	141(55.1%)	38(49.5%)	$\chi^2= 2.931$ p-value=0.087
	Female	115(44.9%)	39(50.6%)	
BirthWeight	Less than 2.5 kg	62(24.2%)	42(67.7%)	$\chi^2=15.503$ p-value<0.001
	2.5 kg or more	181(70.7%)	81(44.8%)	
	Not known	13(5.1%)	11(84.6%)	
Immunization status	Fully Immunized	187(73%)	43(23.00%)	$\chi^2=16.552$ p-value<0.001
	Partially/Not immunized	69(27%)	34(49.30%)	
Mothers education	Illiterate/Primary	63(24.6%)	28(44.40%)	$\chi^2=14.621$ Df-2 p-value=0.001
	Till S.S.C	151(59%)	45(29.80%)	
	Above S.S.C	42(16.4%)	4(9.50%)	
Over crowding	Present	191(74.6%)	68(35.60%)	$\chi^2=10.914$ p-value<0.001
	Absent	65(25.4%)	9(13.80%)	
Family composition	2orless	158(61.7%)	34(21.50%)	$\chi^2=14.337$ p-value<0.001
	3ormore	98(38.3%)	43(43.90%)	
Socio-economic Status	Class I/II	32(12.5%)	2(6.30%)	$\chi^2=21.017$ p-value<0.001
	Class III	74(28.9%)	14(18.90%)	
	Class IV/V	150(58.6%)	61(40.70%)	

Total 256 participants were part of study. Majority were male and belongs to 12-36 months age group. 70.7% children were having birth-weight more than 2.5, whereas 73% children were fully immunized and overcrowding was present in 74.6% houses. Majority (58.6%) belongs to low socioeconomic status. However, all these factors were significantly associated with occurrence of Acute Respiratory infection.

Table 2: Cultural factors influencing ARI status of under-five children

Variable		Sample	ARI cases	χ^2 /P value
Exclusive breastfeeding	Yes	184(71.9%)	39(21.20%)	$\chi^2=24.542$ p-value<0.001
	No	72(28.1%)	38(52.80%)	
Discarding Colostrum	Yes	18(32.8%)	16(88.9%)	$\chi^2=10.366$ p-value=0.001
	No	238(93%)	118(49.6%)	
Pre-lacteal feeds	Yes	68(26.6%)	36(52.90%)	$\chi^2=23.014$ p-value<0.001
	No	188(73.4%)	41(21.80%)	
Early Weaning	Yes	84(32.8%)	62(73.8%)	$\chi^2=23.094$ p-value<0.001

From above table, it can be seen that exclusive breast feeding (71.9%) have negative impact on occurrence of ARI whereas practices of discarding colostrum (88.9%), administration of pre-lacteal feeds (52.90%) and early weaning practices (73.8%) are significantly associated with occurrence of ARI.

Table 3: Distribution of children according to Malnutrition grading and severity of ARI

Grading of Malnutrition	Classification of ARI			Total
	No ARI	Mild ARI	Moderate/Severe ARI	
No malnutrition	111	9	2	122
	91.00%	7.40%	1.60%	47.70%
Mild Malnutrition	44	17	6	67
	65.70%	25.40%	9.00%	26.20%
Moderate/Severe Malnutrition	24	17	26	67
	35.80%	25.40%	38.80%	26.20%
Total	179	43	34	256
	69.90%	16.80%	13.30%	100.00%

$\chi^2=72.629$ df-4 p value<0.001

The percentage of moderate to severe malnourished children having no ARI, mild ARI, and moderate to severe ARI was 35.8%, 25.4% and 38.8% respectively. Similarly, 65% mild malnourished child had no ARI, 25.4% had mild ARI and 9% had moderate to severe ARI episodes. The percentage of well-

nourished children having no ARI, mild ARI, and moderate to severe ARI was 91%, 7.4% and 1.6% respectively.

Thus, severity of ARI has statistically significant association with Malnutrition (p value <0.001).

Table 4: Distribution of presenting symptoms of ARI in ARI cases

Presentingsymptoms	ARI occurrence in children (n=77)	
	Number	Percentage
Fever	56	72.70%
Cough (with or without expectoration)	40	51.90%
Running Nose	65	84.50%
Fast Breathing	10	13%
Chest indrawing	3	3.90%
Other symptoms	16	20.78%

*More than 1 symptoms were present in ARI cases.

Table 5: Health Seeking Behaviour of Respondents

Consultation	Number of Respondents (N=256)	
	Number	Percentage
UHTC	103	40.20%
Private Medical Practitioner	79	30.90%
Home based Remedies	52	20.30%
No treatment taken	22	8.60%
Total	256	100%

Above table showed that 40.2% of the parents consulted UHTC for treatment of disease in children while 30.9% consulted private practitioner.

20.3% parents took home based remedies where 8.6% parents did not take any form of treatment.

Discussion

A total of 256 children were Assessed in the study. The study identified a high prevalence of ARI among under-fives and pointed out various socio-demographic, nutritional, and environmental as the modifiable risk factors. The overall prevalence of ARI was found to be 30.4%. A study done by Farzana Islam, Ratnasharma et al. [4](2013) on Profiling ARI among 370 under-five showed prevalence of ARI to be 26.35%. [4] Studies done by Vinod K. Ramani et al., [6] Suguna E, Kumar S G et al. (2015), [7]Duarte DM et al. [8]Botelho C et al [9]showed similar results. There was no significant difference in Age and sex wise distribution of participants and association of ARI. Our findings can be compared with Gupta KB et al. [5]1980 and Mitra NK et al. (10) 2001Jha AK et al. [11]by Rahman MM et al. [12] The high ARI incidence found in children of 2-3 year age group may be due to their greater exposure to environmental factors. [6]

Incidence of ARI was 52.9% in children with administration of pre-lacteal feeds. Only 21.8% children had ARI in whom no pre-lacteal feeds were given. ARI was absent in 69.9% children with no pre-lacteal feeds. Study done by Abhishek Arun et al. [13] who observed significant association between ARI and pre-lacteal feeding. Occurrence of ARI was more in those children who started pre-lacteal feeding (29.3%) as compared to (16.3%) not started pre-lacteal feeding. Similar finding was observed in study carried out by Biswas A et al., [15] Deb SK et al. [16]& M. R. Savitha et al. [17]ARI was present 21.2% children who were exclusively breast feed whereas 52.8% children had ARI who were not exclusively breast feed. Study done by Jha AK et al. [11] showed that prevalence of ARI in non-exclusively breast feed children was higher (28.6%) as compared to exclusively breast feed children (16.1%).

Malnutrition status of children in our study shows that 52.3% of children had malnourishment among which 26.27% children were having grade I malnutrition. The percentage of children having grade II, grade III and grade IV malnourishment was found 19.1%, 5.9% and 1.2% respectively. 47.7% children were found to be normal. Study done by Abhishek Arun et al. (13) nutritional status of child has direct bearing on children's susceptibility to ARI.

Prevalence of ARI amongst children who had no malnutrition was lowest (19.3%), while it was more in Grade-I to IV malnutrition which showed a

strong correlation between nutritional status and occurrence of ARI observations indicate that nutritional status of child has direct bearing on his susceptibility to ARI. Farzana Islam et al., [4] Prajapati. B et al., [18] Rahman MM et al., [12] Abid Ali Mir et al. [19]etc. showed similar results whereas Duarte DM et al.[8]2000 in study from Brazil reported no association between ARI and nutritional status in under-five years children. Running nose (84.5%) fever (72.7%) and cough (51.9%). Fast breathing was present in (13%) and chest in-drawing was present in (3.9%) indicating moderate to severe cases of ARI. Other symptoms include ear discharge, chest pain, stridor, wheeze, inability to drink water etc. Similar findings were seen in Kumar S G, et al. [7](2014), H.N.Bashour et al. (20) (1994) studies.

A study done by MuraliMadhav et al. [21](1989) showed that the most commonly occurring symptoms of ARI were running nose (87.4 per 100), cough (55.3 per 100) and fever (32 per 100). Fast breathing (20.7 per 100) contributed to moderate to severe cases. 76.75% of cases were found to be mild and 23.25% of cases were found to be moderate to severe cases.

Conclusion

In all, 30.1% of the 256 children surveyed had an ARI. The age range of 25–36 months had a higher incidence. Compared to male children, female children were somewhat more affected. Significant risk factors for ARI included malnutrition, poor vaccination, the practice of delivering pre-lacteal meals, low socioeconomic position, overcrowding, inadequate ventilation, the lack of exclusive breastfeeding, and the number of children in the family. Children of poor socioeconomic class, illiterate moms, and mothers with only a secondary education had a considerably higher incidence of ARI and severity of episodes. The most typical symptoms were cough, fever, and runny nose. The primary medical facility for treating children during ARI episodes was UHTC.

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